

Giant Uterine Leiomyomatosis Mimicking Uterine Sarcoma: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Uterine leiomyomas are the most common benign pelvic neoplasm in women of reproductive age. Although they are generally asymptomatic and small in size, on rare occasions they may reach giant dimensions, representing a diagnostic challenge when their clinical and imaging characteristics mimic malignancy, particularly uterine sarcoma. **Case presentation:** We present the case of a 39-year-old patient with progressive increase in abdominal circumference over several years. Imaging studies revealed a uterine mass measuring approximately 30 cm with areas suggestive of degeneration and mass effect on adjacent abdominal structures, raising the differential diagnosis between uterine leiomyomatosis and leiomyosarcoma. Due to suspicion of malignancy, total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was performed without intraoperative complications and with an estimated blood loss of 200 mL. Histopathological examination confirmed the presence of conventional and degenerated uterine leiomyomas with dystrophic calcification and hyalinization, without evidence of malignancy. The patient had a favorable postoperative course. **Discussion:** Giant uterine leiomyomas constitute an uncommon presentation that may mimic malignant neoplasms, making preoperative diagnosis difficult. In these cases, definitive diagnosis depends on histopathological analysis. **Conclusion:** This case highlights that large tumor size does not necessarily imply malignancy. Timely surgical management and histopathological examination are essential to establish the definitive diagnosis and guide appropriate treatment.

KEYWORDS: giant uterine leiomyoma; uterine leiomyomatosis; uterine sarcoma; pelvic mass; hysterectomy; case report.

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INTRODUCTION

Uterine leiomyomas are the most common benign pelvic neoplasm in women of reproductive age, with an estimated lifetime risk of approximately 70% in Caucasian women and up to 80% in women of African descent. In contrast, uterine sarcomas represent an uncommon group of malignant neoplasms originating in the myometrium or endometrial stroma and are associated with aggressive clinical behavior and poor prognosis. Both entities may clinically present as focal myometrial masses, posing a significant diagnostic challenge for clinicians when differentiating between a benign lesion, such as leiomyoma, and a rare malignant neoplasm.^{1,2}

Among uterine sarcomas, leiomyosarcoma is the subtype that most frequently mimics a leiomyoma, as it commonly presents as a myometrial mass with variable growth. Similarly, other malignant tumors such as endometrial stromal sarcoma may also present as uterine masses, contributing to diagnostic difficulty. In clinical practice, the initial evaluation of a patient with a uterine mass includes assessment of clinical characteristics, risk factors, and imaging findings; however, the clinical manifestations of benign leiomyomas and uterine sarcomas are often indistinguishable. For this reason, in many cases the definitive diagnosis can only be established through histopathological analysis following surgical resection.^{2,3}

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Historically, hysterectomy was the standard treatment for most uterine masses, allowing confirmation of the diagnosis through pathological examination. However, current practice includes multiple conservative therapeutic alternatives for the management of symptomatic leiomyomas, including medical treatments, image-guided procedures such as uterine artery embolization or magnetic resonance-guided focused ultrasound, as well as fertility-preserving surgeries such as myomectomy. Although these strategies have enabled fertility preservation and reduced surgical morbidity, they may also limit tissue acquisition for histopathological analysis, potentially hindering the detection of occult uterine sarcomas.^{1,4}

Therefore, differentiating between benign leiomyomas and uterine sarcomas remains a relevant clinical challenge, as it is necessary to balance the risk of delaying the diagnosis of a malignant neoplasm against the need to avoid unnecessary surgical interventions in the majority of patients presenting with benign uterine tumors.^{3,4}

The following report presents the case of a patient with a large uterine mass initially suspected to be a uterine sarcoma, whose definitive diagnosis was established through histopathological examination after surgical management.

CASE PRESENTATION

We present the case of a 39-year-old female patient undergoing evaluation for a pelvic tumor with an initial suspicion of uterine sarcoma. Regarding her family history, she denied oncologic diseases; however, she reported that both parents had diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension. Regarding her non-pathological personal history, she was born and resides in Mérida, Yucatán; she is single, a homemaker, and completed the first year of high school education. She denied tobacco, alcohol, or illicit drug use. The patient reported a regular diet without specific restrictions and physical activity limited to household activities. She denied known genetic conditions or relevant hereditary diseases.

Regarding pathological history, she denied chronic-degenerative diseases such as diabetes mellitus or systemic arterial hypertension and was not receiving pharmacological treatment. She denied previous surgeries or blood transfusions and reported no known allergies.

Her gynecological and obstetric history included menarche at age 13, with irregular menstrual cycles of 28 × 3–8 days. Gravida 0. She initiated sexual activity at age 35 and reported one sexual partner. She denied the use of contraceptive methods. Cervical cytology and human papillomavirus testing were reported as negative.

The patient reported self-detection of an abdominal mass approximately five years earlier. During the last year, she noted progressive enlargement of the abdominal circumference, prompting medical evaluation and initiation of a diagnostic workup due to suspicion of a uterine

neoplasm. She denied abdominal pain, abnormal uterine bleeding, or other associated symptoms.

Physical examination documented an ECOG functional status of 0. The abdomen was distended due to an abdominal mass arising from the uterus, approximately 12 × 10 cm in size, non-mobile and non-tender on palpation; the uterus was palpable above the pubic symphysis. External genitalia were consistent with age and sex. Gynecological examination revealed a smooth cervix without apparent lesions; on vaginal examination, the cervix measured approximately 2 cm in length, chandelier sign was negative, adnexa were free, and the cul-de-sac was not bulging.

Among the imaging studies performed, pelvic ultrasound reported a markedly enlarged uterus measuring 327 × 113 × 301 mm in sagittal, anteroposterior, and transverse axes, respectively, extending toward the left hypochondrium. It was described as having lobulated contours and heterogeneous echotexture due to multiple rounded lesions compatible with myomas, averaging 28, 43, and 58 mm in size. Color Doppler examination showed moderate internal vascularity. Endometrial thickness was 7 mm. The right ovary measured 49 × 25 × 53 mm with an approximate volume of 36 cc, with a small amount of periovarian fluid measuring approximately 6 cc. The left ovary measured 32 × 19 × 35 mm with a volume of 11 cc and normal morphology, size, and echogenicity. The study concluded the presence of a markedly enlarged uterus with multiple myomas occupying the entire myometrium, recommending further evaluation with computed tomography.

Subsequently, contrast-enhanced computed tomography of the abdomen and pelvis was performed, (Figure 1) revealing a markedly enlarged uterus with loss of its usual morphology and lobulated borders, showing heterogeneous enhancement after contrast administration. The mass measured approximately 18.7 × 12.2 × 30.0 cm, displacing intestinal loops cephalad and compressing the urinary bladder. Dilated and tortuous pelvic vessels were also observed, as well as coarse calcifications and hypodense areas suggestive of necrosis or cystic degeneration. No suspicious pelvic lymphadenopathy was identified, and a small amount of free fluid was observed in the pelvic cavity. The diagnostic impression was a pelvic mass with abdominal extension, with characteristics suggestive of giant uterine leiomyomatosis versus leiomyosarcoma; therefore, clinical correlation and histopathological confirmation were recommended.

Based on the clinical and radiological findings, the differential diagnosis included giant uterine leiomyomatosis versus uterine leiomyosarcoma, given the presence of a large uterine mass with degenerative areas and displacement of abdominal structures.

Admission laboratory tests reported hemoglobin of 10.6 g/dL, without other significant abnormalities.

Based on the clinical course and imaging findings, the patient was evaluated by the gynecologic oncology service and considered a candidate for surgical management for both

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diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was performed. During the procedure, a markedly enlarged uterus measuring approximately 30 cm was identified. (Figure 2). Estimated intraoperative blood loss was approximately 200 mL, with no surgical complications reported.

The surgical specimen was sent for histopathological examination. Macroscopic description revealed a uterus with cervix and adnexa fixed in formalin. The uterine body was multilobulated and congested, with a multilobulated surface due to multiple myomas; the specimen weighed approximately 5300 g and measured 32 × 25 × 23 cm. On sectioning, multiple intramural, subserosal, and submucosal stromal nodules were identified, ranging in size from 17 cm to 1.5 cm, solid on cut surface, heterogeneous, with rubbery areas and well-circumscribed calcifications. The ovaries showed stromal edema, and the fallopian tubes appeared congested.

The final histopathological diagnosis reported a hysterectomy specimen with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy showing chronic cystic-polypoid endocervicitis, simple endometrial hyperplasia without atypia, and conventional and degenerated leiomyomas with dystrophic calcification and hyalinization, ranging from 17 cm to 1.5 cm in diameter. The ovaries showed stromal edema, and the fallopian tubes had no histological abnormalities.

The patient had a favorable immediate postoperative course without complications, with adequate clinical recovery and proper surgical wound healing; therefore, she was discharged with outpatient follow-up in the gynecology clinic. No

intraoperative or postoperative adverse events or complications were recorded.

During outpatient follow-up, the patient demonstrated good tolerance to the surgical procedure and favorable clinical evolution, without evidence of recurrence or treatment-related complications.

No economic, cultural, or language barriers limiting access to diagnosis or treatment were identified.

Figure 1. Axial computed tomography scan of the abdomen and pelvis showing a large uterine mass with internal calcifications and mass effect on adjacent abdominal structures, findings consistent with giant uterine leiomyomatosis.

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Figure 2. Surgical specimen following total abdominal hysterectomy showing a markedly enlarged uterus with multiple subserosal and intramural leiomyomas, responsible for the significant deformity and increased uterine volume.

DISCUSSION

Giant uterine leiomyomas represent an uncommon presentation of a common gynecological condition and may pose a significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, especially when their clinical and imaging characteristics mimic malignancy. In our case, the patient presented with a large uterine mass showing progressive growth and computed tomography findings suggestive of uterine leiomyomatosis versus leiomyosarcoma, requiring consideration of a malignant uterine neoplasm in the differential diagnosis. However, definitive histopathological examination confirmed the presence of conventional and degenerated leiomyomas with dystrophic calcification and hyalinization, without evidence of malignancy.^{1,3,4}

The literature describes cases of giant uterine leiomyomas that may generate both diagnostic and surgical difficulties. Mongan and Wibowo reported the case of a 45-year-old patient with a large abdominal mass initially suspected to be an ovarian malignancy; however, during surgery, a markedly enlarged uterus with cystic degeneration of a leiomyoma was identified, and the diagnosis was confirmed histopathologically. The mass measured 57 × 51 cm and weighed 26 kg.⁶ Similarly, in our case, the patient presented with a giant uterine mass with preoperative suspicion of malignancy, raising the differential diagnosis of leiomyosarcoma. Nevertheless, the definitive diagnosis was established through histopathological examination following surgical resection, confirming uterine leiomyomas with degenerative changes.

The literature also describes cases of giant uterine leiomyomas reaching extraordinary dimensions and causing diagnostic difficulties. Wiesener et al. reported the case of a patient with a uterine fibroid exceeding 50 cm in size, which had grown slowly over approximately 15 years and was

initially mistaken for weight gain or abdominal fat.⁷ Similarly, in our case, the patient presented with a giant uterine mass with progressive growth and initial suspicion of malignancy. Both cases highlight how prolonged growth of leiomyomas may cause significant abdominal distension and represent a diagnostic challenge, even in the current era of imaging studies. Furthermore, these reports emphasize the importance of adequate clinical and imaging evaluation to avoid delays in diagnosis and to allow timely surgical management.

The presence of giant uterine leiomyomas is not necessarily associated with malignancy. Brito et al. reported the case of a 49-year-old patient with a 13.5 kg giant uterine leiomyoma treated by total abdominal hysterectomy, in which histopathological examination ruled out malignancy. The authors emphasized that although the large size of a uterine mass may raise suspicion of malignant neoplasia, most of these tumors correspond to benign lesions.⁸ Similarly, in our case, the patient presented with a giant uterine mass and preoperative suspicion of uterine sarcoma; however, histopathological analysis confirmed uterine leiomyomas with degenerative changes and no evidence of malignancy. These findings reinforce that tumor size alone is not a reliable criterion for predicting malignancy in uterine masses.

Among the strengths of this case management was the integration of clinical evaluation, imaging studies, and surgical treatment with histopathological confirmation, which allowed establishment of a definitive diagnosis. Furthermore, the surgical approach was appropriate for a large uterine mass with suspicion of malignancy, achieving complete resection without intraoperative complications and with relatively low estimated blood loss considering the complexity of the procedure. Another favorable aspect was the patient's satisfactory postoperative recovery.

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As limitations, it should be noted that despite support from ultrasonography and computed tomography, it was not possible to conclusively differentiate between giant leiomyoma and leiomyosarcoma prior to surgery. This reflects a known limitation of current diagnostic tools in large uterine masses with degenerative changes. Additionally, given the chronic growth of the lesion, delayed specialized medical attention may have contributed to the tumor reaching such dimensions at the time of treatment.

This case provides several relevant clinical lessons. First, giant uterine leiomyomas remain an important cause of abdominopelvic masses and may mimic malignant neoplasms. Second, suspicion of leiomyosarcoma should be considered in large uterine masses with progressive growth and degenerative imaging changes; however, definitive diagnosis still depends on histopathological examination. Finally, timely and well-planned surgical management allows safe and definitive treatment, even in giant uterine tumors.

The patient reported having noticed progressive abdominal enlargement over several years, initially without associating it with a gynecological disease. The increase in abdominal volume caused concern about the possibility of malignancy; however, after learning the definitive benign diagnosis following surgery, she expressed relief and satisfaction with the treatment outcome.

CONCLUSION

Giant uterine leiomyomas represent an uncommon presentation of a common gynecological condition and may constitute a diagnostic challenge, particularly when their clinical and imaging characteristics raise suspicion of malignancy. This case highlights the difficulty of preoperatively differentiating between leiomyoma and uterine sarcoma, especially in large masses with degenerative changes. Nevertheless, definitive diagnosis continues to depend on histopathological examination. Furthermore, this case demonstrates that large tumor size does not necessarily imply malignancy and that timely surgical management allows definitive and safe treatment with favorable postoperative outcomes.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, interventions performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as

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